

INTERACTIVE LISTENING ACTIVITIES: DESIGN LISTENING
EXERCISES THAT ADAPT TO STUDENTS' LEVELS WITH AI
SUPPORT

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Annotation: The use of technology in language learning has become increasingly prevalent in recent years, with a growing body of literature exploring the benefits and drawbacks of its integration in the classroom. In the article designing listening exercises that adapt to students' levels with AI support was discussed.

Key words: *artificial intelligence, adaptive learning experiences, Traditional approaches, video-based activities, cultural references, language proficiency, active listening.*

English holds a vital role in today's interconnected world. For ESL (English as a Second Language) or EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students, learning English can be a challenging but rewarding journey. With the advancement of technology, AI-powered language learning tools offer innovative ways to enhance students' language acquisition. These tools utilize artificial intelligence to provide personalized and adaptive learning experiences. Through interactive activities, AI can assist ESL students in developing their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills, catering to their individual learning styles and needs. Listening skills are a crucial component of language learning, as they allow learners to comprehend and respond appropriately to spoken language. However, many

foreign language learners struggle with developing their listening skills, which can hinder their ability to communicate effectively in the target language.

Traditional approaches to teaching listening skills, such as textbook exercises and scripted dialogues, may not be engaging enough for learners, especially in the case of younger learners. This is where technology comes in as a powerful tool to enhance the learning experience by providing interactive and authentic activities that can motivate learners and improve their listening skills. Technology has become an integral part of language education, offering new opportunities to develop learners' listening skills in engaging and interactive ways. The use of technology enables teachers to incorporate a range of authentic materials, such as TV shows, movies, and podcasts, into their lessons, providing learners with exposure to natural language use and culture[1]. Moreover, the use of software tools and multimedia resources makes it easier to design effective listening activities that can cater to learners' different needs and preferences. In recent years, there has been growing interest in the potential of technology to enhance language learning, particularly in developing listening skills. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of technology-enhanced listening activities in improving learners' listening comprehension, motivation, and engagement[2]. (For example, podcasts have been found to be a useful tool for developing learners' listening skills, as they provide authentic language input and opportunities for learners to practice listening independently. Similarly, video-based activities, such as watching TV shows or movies, can help learners develop their listening skills by providing exposure to different accents, intonation patterns, and cultural references. However, incorporating technology into language teaching is not without its challenges. Teachers need to carefully select and design technology-enhanced listening activities that are appropriate for their learners' level, interests, and goals. Moreover, teachers need to have the necessary

technological skills and resources to design and implement these activities effectively.

Vitta and Al-Hoorie (2020) conducted a meta-analysis of 56 reports on the use of technology in language learning, finding that technology had a positive effect on learners' language proficiency, particularly in areas such as reading and listening comprehension[3]. Similarly, Lan (2022) conducted a study with Taiwanese university students and found that the use of multimedia materials such as audio and video clips improved their listening skills and motivation to learn. More specifically, several studies have explored the use of YouTube in language learning[4]. Almurashi (2016) conducted a literature review on the role of YouTube in teaching English as a foreign language, finding that it offered a range of benefits including exposure to authentic materials, increased motivation, and opportunities for learner autonomy[5]. Husna, Purnawarman, Suherdi and Lubis (2019) conducted a systematic review of 14 studies on the use of multimedia in EFL classrooms, finding that YouTube was one of the most commonly used resources and that it had a positive impact on learners' language proficiency. The demand for learning English is increasing day by day. In particular, the interest in learning foreign languages in our country has increased to several percent compared to the situation a few years ago. Several decrees aimed at the development of foreign languages by our government can serve as a prove of our opinion. In expressing my opinion as a student of this field, I should highlighted that every student who wants to learn English perfectly should study these four skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. These skills are inextricably linked with each other, for example, mastering listening comprehension helps to become a good speaker. The usage of innovative methods in improving listening comprehension skills gives great help to those who master this skill, especially to those who have just started learning. Based on my personal practice, listening to many English audios, listening to songs in English and watching movies in this

language are the most important factors in improving listening comprehension skills.

A great opportunity to improve your active listening skills is Active listening exercises and it has some fun. Being an active listener can come naturally and can be developed. For effective communication, active listening skills is very important. If you are not a good listener, then never can be a good communicator. Active listening skills are crucial in every aspect of your life, both personal and professional. Research also suggests that active listening has many health benefits such as better learning, improved memory, treatment of anxiety disorders, etc. Active listening refers to the process of listening carefully and understanding what the other person is saying[6]. This listening method makes the speaker feel heard and valued. Active listening skills are the ability to listen carefully and make a conscious effort to understand the speaker's messages.

Mainly active listening is about making the speaker feel heard. As an active listener, you need to pay full attention and show it. These exercises will help you show your audience that you are paying attention to their messages.

1. List examples of good and bad listening skills you know. Good listening skills include nodding, smiling, maintaining eye contact, showing empathy, etc. Poor listening skills may include looking at your phone or watch, fidgeting, interrupting, rehearsing answers, etc. This exercise will make you aware of avoidance skills and developing skills.

2. Ask someone to share their experience. Ask your friends or family members, especially two, to share stories from their past. For example, when the person was hospitalized on the first day at university, etc. When you're listening in the first person, try asking questions. Then, share a similar experience as you listen to the other person and ask each speaker when they feel heard and respected.

3. 3-Minutes Off. In this activity, the speaker talks for three minutes about their dream vacation. The speaker should describe what he wants from the holiday

but without specifying a destination. When the speaker is speaking, the listener pays attention and uses only nonverbal cues to indicate interest in what the speaker is saying. After 3 minutes, the listener must summarize the key points of the speaker's dream vacation and then guess the name of the destination. The speaker then reviews how close the listener was to what was said and needed. Also, the speaker discusses the listener's nonverbal cues.

4. Discuss a common topic with your friend. Pair up with your friend and discuss a common topic. For example, inflation. Each of you should be a speaker or a listener. When the speaker has finished speaking, the audience should repeat the speaker's main points and praise them.

5. Many-to-one versus one-to-one. Have a group conversation with your friends. At a time allow one person to speak. Then, conversation with each of them one by one. Ask, when have they heard the most? Does the number of participants matter?

6. Paraphrase what the speaker said. Ask your friend to tell you about yourself — his favorite books, bad experiences in life, etc. When he speaks, maintain positive body language such as nodding and verbal affirmations such as "I agree", "I understand", etc. When your friend (the speaker) has finished speaking, repeat what he said. For example, "I heard you say that your favorite actor..."

Active listening is not just about giving the speaker a sense of being heard or non-verbal cues. It requires listeners to make a conscious effort to remember what they hear. At this point, it should be noted that creating an English atmosphere not only improves English speaking but also listening skills. In the organization of English lessons, the creation of an English language environment by the teachers will increase the students' interest in learning the language, and of course, the percentage of mastering an interestingly organized lesson will be at the highest level. In our country, the listening ability of the students is not adapted to the

English language because the environment of the English language is rare and this is the biggest obstacle in acquiring this qualification[7]. Because the more we listen, the more we understand the language we listen to. During my practice, I used various interesting games and different handouts according to developing listening skill. On the other hand, showing videos on the topic gave the best result in my practice. It is increasingly recognized that being one of the most crucial aspects of foreign language (FL) acquisition listening comprehension (LC) yet remains deficient in support; on the other hand, it is at the core of many debated issues in the areas of bilingual education and FL pedagogy. This can be accounted for by constant accumulating the data that prove the significance of LC. The evidence seems to be cogent that LC should be prioritized in the process of FL acquisition. Consequently, it will be plausible to premise that a considerable amount of research needs to be undertaken in this domain, since the generating interest in the subject under investigation still raises a sufficient number of controversies.

Summing up all given information it should be noted that listening has also been examined in relation not only to comprehension but also to language learning in the recent years. Since listening can provide much of the input and data that learners receive in language learning, an important question is: How can attention to the language the listener hears facilitate second language learning? This raises the issue of the role “noticing” and conscious awareness of language form play, and how noticing can be part of the process by which learners can incorporate new word forms and structures into their developing communicative competence. Listening is key to all effective communication. Without the ability to listen effectively, messages are easily misunderstood. As a result, communication breaks down and the sender of the message can easily become frustrated or irritated. If there is one communication skill you should aim to master, then listening is it. Listening is so important that many top employers provide listening skills training

for their employees. This is not surprising when you consider that good listening skills can lead to better customer satisfaction, greater productivity with fewer mistakes, and increased sharing of information that in turn can lead to more creative and innovative work.

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